

Review article

Hybrid construction featuring wire arc additive manufacturing: review, concepts, challenges and opportunities

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ABSTRACT

Wire arc additive manufacturing (WAAM) offers a level of geometric flexibility and automation that has yet to be seen in construction, and brings new opportunities to optimise material use in structures and reduce embodied carbon. Despite the advantages of AM, the relatively low productivity and high cost are a major barrier to its wider application in construction. In this context, a form of hybrid construction, in which conventional structural elements are coupled with WAAM, has emerged and is the focus of the present paper. The concept is to utilise the efficiency of established manufacturing methods such as hot-rolling or cold-forming to produce the bulk of a structure, but to exploit the geometric freedom of WAAM to make targeted additions that bring about disproportionate benefits. These benefits could be in terms of improved structural performance and efficiency, material savings, weight reductions, reductions in environmental impact, increased automation or reduced costs. By limiting printing only to the parts that require the geometric flexibility offered by WAAM, hybrid construction increases the viability of using this technology in practice. A review of applications of the hybrid construction concept is presented, covering a range of scenarios including the strengthening of structural members, the addition of structural details, the creation of joints, the repair of damaged elements and the facilitation of reuse. The importance of structural optimisation is highlighted, the effects of thermally-induced residual stresses and deformations are discussed and the implications on carbon emissions are explored. Finally, an outlook for the industrialisation of the described form of hybrid construction featuring WAAM, including the key challenges and opportunities in terms of sustainability, economic viability, printability, multi-material and on-site construction applications and structural design, is set out.

1. Introduction

The building and construction sector, which accounts for about 20 % of global carbon emissions [1], is facing an unprecedented challenge to decarbonise. Given that the current material utilisation rate in structures is typically below 50 % [2], there is significant scope to reduce material consumption and hence embodied carbon in construction. However, a major barrier to achieving this is the limited geometric flexibility of conventional steelwork manufacturing methods such as hot-rolling or cold-forming. These manufacturing methods generally lend themselves only to the production of prismatic structural elements, the uniform nature of which rarely provides an efficient match to the structural demands. Metal additive manufacturing (AM), on the other hand, is a novel, digitally-enabled technology that allows metal parts to be created in a layer-by-layer fashion with almost no restrictions on geometry, and lends itself to the production of intricate, optimised structural elements

that have not been practical thus far. Metal AM is therefore emerging as a potential catalyst for a more sustainable and more automated construction industry.

Metal AM can be divided into four main categories – directed energy deposition (DED), powder bed fusion (PBF), binder jetting (BJT) and sheet lamination (SHL). Wire arc additive manufacturing (WAAM) is a wire-based DED method with, in comparison with other means of metal AM, relatively high deposition rates, large build volumes, low costs, good mechanical properties, reasonable geometric resolution and readily available feedstock material (i.e. welding wire). It has therefore been widely recognised that WAAM has great promise for adoption in construction [3]. An increasing amount of fundamental research has been conducted to investigate the mechanical properties of WAAM materials in the context of structural engineering, mainly covering carbon steels [4–10] and stainless steels [11–17]. The experimental results have shown generally sound material properties, but also

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challenges associated with surface undulations, anisotropic behaviour, the influence of process parameters, printing defects and an overall higher variability (in terms of both geometric and mechanical properties) than conventionally produced structural steel elements. A growing body of experiments on WAAM structural elements in conventional geometric forms, including cross-sections [18–23], members [24,25] and connections [26–30], has revealed their largely comparable structural performance to corresponding conventionally produced elements. Dot-by-dot printing, a variant of WAAM where material is deposited through a series of discontinuous welding dots as opposed to continuous welding, has also attracted growing research interest [31–37]. Several demonstration projects, such as the landmark MX3D bridge in Amsterdam [38–40], a footbridge printed in-situ at TU Darmstadt [41], a series of optimised trusses [42,43] and an optimised garden bridge in London [44], as shown in Fig. 1, have shown the feasibility of WAAM to produce large-scale, intricate geometries for structural applications.

Although WAAM technology is rapidly evolving, it is unlikely that it will ever be competitive against conventional structural steel manufacturing processes for the construction of complete building, bridges etc in terms of productivity, energy consumption and costs. In this context, a novel hybrid construction concept has emerged, in which the bulk of a structure is produced by conventional manufacturing methods, and a relatively small amount of WAAM material, strategically located, is used in a complementary fashion. This allows the geometric flexibility of WAAM to be exploited, while retaining the merits of conventional steel manufacturing, thereby achieving a balance between enhancement in structural efficiency, productivity and economic viability. This concept shares a similar principle to hybrid manufacturing, a process that combines different manufacturing technologies to overcome their individual limitations, and that has gained substantial traction in manufacturing engineering [45,46]. Hybrid construction, a translation of hybrid manufacturing into the

construction industry, is deemed to be a viable pathway towards the widespread adoption of WAAM for structural engineering purposes.

In this paper, a review of the existing research themed around hybrid construction, including a collection of ongoing studies at Imperial College London, is described. The applications of the hybrid construction concept covers various structural settings, including the strengthening of columns, beams and tension members, the local strengthening of cross-sections under concentrated transverse loading and plated elements, structural joints, and the repair of damaged elements, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The scope for structural optimisation, the impact of printing on existing structures in terms of residual stresses and thermal deformations and the implications on carbon emissions are discussed throughout. Following the research advances, the key challenges and opportunities associated with hybrid construction, in terms of sustainability, economic viability, printability, multi-material and on-site construction and structural design, are set out and discussed.

2. Strengthening of members

This section presents a series of studies featuring targeted additions of WAAM material to enhance the structural performance of conventionally manufactured structural steel members serving as columns, beams and tension members. The concepts of structural strengthening using WAAM can be employed in the context of both new construction and the rehabilitation of existing infrastructure, although the latter requires the technological readiness for on-site printing, as discussed later in Section 6.5. Some of the strengthening strategies are applicable also to conventional manufacturing methods, yet WAAM offers additional benefits of enhanced automation, a simplified supply chain and considerable scope for optimisation, and could be the favoured option in many scenarios.

(a) MX3D bridge in Amsterdam, the Netherlands [38–40]

(b) Footbridge in Darmstadt [41]

(c) Optimised trusses [42,43]

(d) Imperial-Shimizu optimised garden bridge in London [44]

Fig. 1. Demonstration WAAM steel structures.

Fig. 2. Concept of hybrid construction in various structural engineering scenarios (conventionally produced steel components in grey, WAAM parts in red).

2.1. Columns

Gardner et al. [47] explored the use of WAAM to strengthen conventional hot-rolled steel I-section columns against minor axis flexural buckling. WAAM steel stiffeners, in different configurations, were added to the flange tips, as illustrated in Fig. 3, where the WAAM material is indicated in red. As shown in Fig. 4, the addition of WAAM stiffeners provides three mechanisms of strengthening: (a) increasing the cross-sectional area and second moment of area about the minor axis, and thus the flexural buckling resistance about the minor axis; (b) restricting local displacements at the flange tips, similar to lipped stiffeners in cold-formed steel profiles, and hence enhancing the resistance to local/distortional buckling, and (c) thermally introducing a favourable residual stress pattern featuring high tensile residual stresses (as opposed to the usual compressive residual stresses) at the flange tips

Fig. 3. Different WAAM stiffener profiles for the strengthening of hot-rolled I-section columns.

[48], as illustrated in Fig. 5 (where σ is the measured residual stress, with compression positive, and f_y is the yield strength), delaying the onset of first yield upon minor axis buckling.

The strengthened hot-rolled steel I-section column specimens with different member lengths and stiffener configurations, along with corresponding bare I-section specimens (i.e. without WAAM stiffeners), serving as benchmarks, were tested under axial compression with pinned boundary conditions; typical failure modes and load-deflection curves obtained from the experiments are shown in Figs. 6 and 7 respectively. Compared with the bare I-sections, disproportionate increases in buckling strength of between 17 % and 54 % were achieved for increases of mass of between 2 % and 26 % by the WAAM-strengthened members, underlining the potential for significant enhancements in structural efficiency and for reducing material consumption and carbon emissions. It is worth noting that, in addition to inducing residual stresses, the complex thermal history associated with WAAM also inevitably causes conventional steel members to deform during printing. In the case of columns where geometric imperfections are detrimental, careful toolpath planning and printing sequencing should be exercised to minimise the thermal distortions. Note that there remains considerable scope for optimisation of the WAAM stiffener profiles; such research is currently underway at Imperial College London.

2.2. Beams

A further recent study employed WAAM to enhance the performance of hot-rolled steel I-section beams [49]. In this case, WAAM material has been deposited longitudinally onto the beam flanges. The added WAAM material effectively increases the section modulus of the beams and, for the material deposited onto the tips of the compression flanges, reduces the cross-sectional susceptibility to local buckling. The profile of the WAAM material can be tailored to match the bending moment distribution arising within the beam. Furthermore, as opposed to columns, where thermal deformations are to be minimised, in beams, the WAAM material can be deposited onto the tension flange to purposely introduce a pre-camber in the members by thermal contraction, as shown in Fig. 8,

Fig. 4. Mechanisms of strengthening achieved by the addition of WAAM stiffeners [47].

Fig. 5. Change of residual stress patterns in hot-rolled steel I-section due to WAAM strengthening [48].

which effectively increases the permitted vertical deflections at the serviceability limit state. The WAAM strengthened and bare (i.e. without WAAM material) hot-rolled steel I-section beam specimens have been tested under three-point and four-point bending about their major axis with lateral restraint provided; a typical tested WAAM-strengthened

Fig. 6. Typical WAAM-strengthened I-section column specimen after testing [47].

specimen is displayed in Fig. 9. The results showed that a considerable increase in the initial stiffness and bending moment capacity with reduced net vertical deflections was achieved for the strengthened beams compared with the benchmark bare I-section beams, as illustrated in Fig. 10. A similar concept to enhance the performance of hot-rolled steel I-sections in bending using WAAM was prototyped by Kloft et al. [50], as shown in Fig. 11.

2.3. Tension members

Another study that is currently underway is seeking to strengthen conventionally produced steel circular hollow section (CHS) members in tension using WAAM. WAAM high strength steel material has been deposited longitudinally around the circumference of S355 steel CHS members, as depicted in Fig. 12. In addition to the increase of cross-

Fig. 7. Typical load-mid-height lateral deflection curves from buckling tests on plain and WAAM-strengthened I-section columns [47].

Fig. 8. Pre-cambering effect on I-section beams from addition of WAAM material to tension flange.

Fig. 9. Typical WAAM-strengthened I-section beam specimen after testing.

Fig. 10. Comparison of moment-deflection curves for WAAM-strengthened and bare I-section beams.

sectional area and yield strength, compressive residual stresses are thermally introduced into the conventional CHS, delaying the full cross-section yielding and further enhancing the yield load of the member in tension. Additionally, combining high strength steel with mild steel could mitigate the inferior ductility of the former, a notable issue hindering the wider use of high strength steel in structural applications [51–54]. An anticipated challenge is that the addition of WAAM material would inevitably cause thermal distortions in the conventional steel members, which need to be controlled during printing, for example, by optimising the printing sequence.

Fig. 11. WAAM stiffeners for hot-rolled steel I-section in bending [50].

3. Local strengthening of cross-sections

Structural cross-sections prone to localised buckling are commonly strengthened by the manual welding of stiffening plates. WAAM provides a new means of local strengthening, offering greater material efficiency through optimisation and a higher level of automation than manual welding. In this section, the use of WAAM to strengthen structural sections subjected to concentrated loading and generic plated elements, is explored. As discussed previously in Section 2, the concepts of local strengthening discussed herein are applicable to both new and existing structures, and some also remain feasible for conventional

Fig. 12. Concept of WAAM-strengthened CHS in tension.

manufacturing methods.

3.1. Cross-sections under transverse concentrated loading

For structural cross-sections under concentrated transverse loading, transverse stiffeners are commonly adopted to enhance the resistance to web crippling. Lange et al. [55] demonstrated the feasibility of adding transverse stiffeners onto hot-rolled steel I-sections via WAAM, as shown in Fig. 13, and highlighted the advantages of WAAM in accommodating the geometric tolerances of conventional steel profiles and the potential for reducing material usage through optimisation. Kloft et al. [50] explored the use of WAAM to strengthen hot-rolled steel I-sections under internal one-flange and two-flange loading. The WAAM stiffeners were optimised based on either (a) the distribution of the second-order bending moment in the stiffener after buckling, or (b) the progression of the principal stresses in the web. To manufacture the optimised stiffeners shown in Fig. 14, adjustments to the toolpaths and the process parameters were needed to address the challenges arising from the geometric imperfections, the obstruction from the flanges, the connection to the flange walls and the thermal deformations, to which more automated solutions are desired in future studies.

An optimisation study is currently underway at Imperial College London, aiming to derive optimal WAAM stiffener profiles to explicitly maximise the load-carrying capacity of hot-rolled I-sections under concentrated loading, as shown in Fig. 15. The stiffener profile was initially informed by linear topology optimisation, parameterised (as illustrated in Fig. 15, where c_1 and b_1 – b_3 are the widths of the stiffener at key locations and t_1 and t_2 are the thicknesses), and subsequently optimised using particle swarm optimisation (PSO) following a similar approach to that employed in [56]. This allows geometric and material nonlinearities to be incorporated in the maximisation of load-carrying capacity, with some compromises on the geometric flexibility.

Fig. 13. Transverse stiffeners for hot-rolled steel I-section manufactured by WAAM [55].

Fig. 14. Optimised WAAM stiffeners for hot-rolled steel I-sections under internal one-flange loading (left) and internal two-flange loading (right) [50].

3.2. Plates

By selectively depositing WAAM material onto plates, their mechanical behaviour, including the stiffness, strength and susceptibility to local buckling, can be disproportionately improved. Tankova and Veljkovic [57] studied the optimisation of WAAM stiffeners for plates under various loading scenarios, including uniaxial compression, shear and biaxial compression. The considered WAAM stiffeners were in a plated form with varying depths and thicknesses, with or without openings, as illustrated in Fig. 16. The finite element analysis revealed that similar elastic buckling stress and ultimate load to those for the conventional prismatic plate stiffener can be achieved by the optimised WAAM stiffeners with material savings up to 20 %. In terms of the ultimate buckling resistance, the thermally induced distortions and residual stresses could have an adverse effect, which should be considered in future studies. It is worth mentioning that in other industries, such as aerospace and automotive, researchers have also been exploring the use of WAAM for local stiffening of e.g. flat plates [58], curved plates [59] and car parts [60], as shown in Fig. 17, which may be translated into structural engineering applications.

4. Joints

The fabrication of steelwork joints is currently a somewhat labour-intensive process. Using WAAM to create structural joints, which represent only a small portion of the structure, mitigates the limitations of WAAM in terms of productivity and costs, and also brings scope for optimisation and automation. Particularly in cases where local joint limit states governs member selection, the adoption of optimised WAAM joints could avoid upsizing the connected steel members and bring about considerable savings in overall material consumptions. Arup was among the first to explore the adoption of metal AM to fabricate a series of topology optimised nodes for a tensegrity structure, as shown in Fig. 18 (a) [61]; the nodes were printed in stainless steel using powder bed fusion (PBF). MX3D and Takenaka designed and produced the first

Fig. 15. Parameterisation and optimisation of WAAM stiffeners for I-section under internal two-flange loading.

Fig. 16. Illustration of WAAM stiffener for steel plate [57].

WAAM stainless steel structural connectors, as shown in Fig. 18(b) [62].

In this section, several endeavours to create structural joints using metal AM, featuring varying extents of structural optimisation, are presented; the primary focus is on WAAM, while some notable studies featuring other methods of metal AM are also included in the discussion.

4.1. Joints between beams and columns

Lange et al. [55] proposed a series of conceptual joint designs featuring WAAM, including a beam hook (Fig. 19(a)) to form pinned connections between I-section beams and columns, and topology optimised connectors to create I-section beam splices (Fig. 19(b)); for the latter, it was shown numerically that compared with conventional end plate connections, only 40 % of the mass was needed for the optimised WAAM connectors to achieve the same load-carrying capacity as the conventional counterpart.

An ongoing study at Imperial College London seeks to develop optimised metal AM joints between I-section beam and box section columns. Linear topology optimisation was conducted to maximise the stiffness of the joint. A typical optimised joint, to be printed onto the box column face and bolted to the I-section beam, is displayed in Fig. 20. Following a similar concept, Afshar Imani et al. [63] carried out an investigation to optimise an I-section beam-to-I-section column joint for additive manufacturing, in which an extended bi-directional structural optimisation (BESO) technique was adopted to incorporate material and geometric nonlinearities in the topology optimisation. Compared with the fully welded joint of the same volume, the topology optimised joints were shown by the finite element modelling to achieve a significant increase in stiffness, ultimate moment capacity (up to 73 %) and ductility.

(a) PBF topology optimised nodes by Arup [61]

(b) WAAM connector by MX3D and Takenaka [62]

Fig. 18. Conceptual structural nodes created using metal AM.

4.2. Joints in trusses and spatial grid structures

Taking inspiration from bamboo, Kanyilmaz et al. [64] numerically investigated the optimisation and structural behaviour of joints between tubular members. Topology optimisation was conducted to maximise the joint stiffness under a defined stress constraint, the results from which were shown to resemble the geometry of bamboo culms, as shown in Fig. 21. Linear analysis showed that compared with conventional

(a) WAAM grid stiffeners for a flat panel after machining [58]

(b) WAAM stiffeners for a curved panel [59]

(c) WAAM stiffeners for car parts [60]

Fig. 17. WAAM strengthening of plated elements in aerospace and automotive industries.

Fig. 19. WAAM connectors between I-section beams and columns [55].

Fig. 20. Topology optimised joint between conventionally produced I-section beam and box section column.

Fig. 21. Bamboo-inspired topology optimised tubular joints [64].

joints of a similar weight, the topology optimised joints exhibited lower peak stress levels, which is beneficial to the fatigue behaviour. Chen et al. [65] adopted BESO for linear topology optimisation of the nodes in 3D spatial grid trusses, considering multiple load cases derived from the

Fig. 22. PBF topology optimised joint in spatial grid structures [65].

finite element modelling of the entire truss structure. Selected optimised nodes were manufactured in stainless steel using PBF, as shown in Fig. 22, where the circular ends were intended for welding to conventional steel tubular truss members. Huang et al. [66] experimentally compared the compressive behaviour of conventional and optimised PBF stainless steel tubular X-joints. The test results on the optimised joints showed very good energy dissipation and thus promising seismic behaviour, despite limited enhancements in the ultimate load-carrying capacity due to the inability to account for buckling in linear topology optimisation.

As part of the ongoing PIONEER project [67], a hybrid planar truss based on the WAAM optimised trusses presented in [43] is being developed. For the hybrid design, as illustrated in Fig. 23, conventionally rolled CHS members are used in place of the truss chords and braces, and the truss nodes are optimised and to be produced using WAAM. The aim is to achieve comparable structural performance to the original fully printed trusses, but with much less WAAM material used to substantially reduce the production time and costs.

For grid-shell structures, nodes are typically used to connect multiple members meeting at different angles, and are often the bottleneck in terms of structural design and manufacture. There have been a number of studies into the optimisation of nodes in grid-shell structures for metal AM [68–71]; two prototypes, printed in stainless steel using binder jetting [70,71], are shown in Fig. 24. Ariza [72] explored the use of WAAM, with a particular focus on dot-by-dot printing, to join tubular

Fig. 23. Concept of hybrid truss featuring optimised WAAM nodes.

Fig. 24. Typical metal AM optimised nodes in grid-shell structures [70,71].

Fig. 25. Typical dot-by-dot printed connection between tubular members in spatial structures (left) and preliminary topology optimisation results (right) [72].

Fig. 26. Hybrid manufacturing of lattice structure featuring WAAM and DSAW for improved productivity [73].

members in spatial structures, and the scope for optimisation was also highlighted – see Fig. 25. Most research has been focussed on optimisation, finite element modelling and prototyping, while experimental verification of optimised AM joints (e.g. [70]) remains rather scarce.

Aiming for higher productivity, Riegger et al. [73] combined WAAM with drawn-arc stud welding (DASW), a method for full area welding of metal studs onto a base metal, for the manufacture of large-scale steel lattice structures. WAAM was used to produce the geometrically complex nodes, while DASW was adopted in a robotic manner to join steel studs, which represent the straight segments of the lattice structure, onto the WAAM nodes. Through the manufacture of a representative part of a lattice structure, as shown in Fig. 26, the hybrid approach was shown to achieve a lower maximum temperature due to less heat input, and a reduction in production time of almost 60 % compared with the fully WAAM approach.

4.3. Hybrid joints

The strategy behind most research thus far in this area is to replace

Fig. 27. Hybrid joints between conventionally produced CHS members [74,75].

conventional joints entirely with metal AM parts. Lincoln Electric proposed an alternative hybrid approach to the manufacture of conventional steel circular hollow section (CHS) joints [74]. The CHS chord remains continuous, while WAAM material is deposited onto the chord face up to a certain length to facilitate welding of the brace member; these types of joints are termed hybrid joints herein, as opposed to fully printed joints. A prototype of this approach is shown in Fig. 27. With a small amount of WAAM material, the proposed approach avoids the need for tube profiling, simplifies welding, improves welding access, relocates the manual welds away from the highly stressed member intersections to improve fatigue performance, and brings scope for joint strengthening. A similar approach was also described by Müglitz et al. [75], as also shown in Fig. 27.

Inspired by this hybrid approach, the use of WAAM to strengthen conventional welded T-joints between square and rectangular hollow section (SHS and RHS respectively) members is being explored as part of the ongoing PIONEER project [67]. Linear topology optimisation has been performed to determine the optimal strategy for the addition of

Fig. 28. GMNIA results for bare and hybrid T-joints with topology optimised WAAM stiffeners (in red).

Fig. 29. Bolted connections between conventionally produced and WAAM steel T-stubs [28].

Fig. 30. Hybrid sleeve connections between conventionally produced CHS members and WAAM parts [76].

WAAM material to maximise the joint stiffness. It was revealed from the geometrically and materially nonlinear analysis with imperfections (GMNIA), as shown in Fig. 28, that disproportionate increases in both the initial stiffness and load-carrying capacity are achieved by the hybrid joints, since the added WAAM material spreads the compressive force from the brace to the stiffener chord face-web junctions over a wider region. Experimental verification of the optimised hybrid joints is currently underway.

4.4. Connections between WAAM and conventional parts

Complementary to the research on metal AM joints for hybrid structures, a number of studies have been devoted to connections between metal AM and conventionally produced parts. Several

experimental investigations into standard bolted connections between WAAM and conventional steel plated elements, including single- and double-lap shear bolted connections and T-stub connections, have been conducted [26–30], as shown in Fig. 29. The ultimate loads from the experiments were found to be generally well predicted by the existing codified design methods for conventional steel connections.

A recent study reported by Meng et al. [76] explored an effective means of connecting conventional CHS members to metal AM tubular parts, in which a novel bolted sleeve connector was proposed and experimentally verified, as shown in Fig. 30. The experiments demonstrated the suitability of the proposed sleeve connections for use in e.g. hybrid tubular trusses and grid-shell structures, and also revealed challenges associated with the early loss of stiffness and practical assembly.

5. Repair of damaged elements and facilitating reuse

The ability of metal AM to add material in a targeted manner can be leveraged to repair damaged components in existing structures, or to adapt end-of-life structural elements to facilitate reuse, which has significant sustainability benefits. Several proof-of-concept studies into the use of metal AM, particularly WAAM, for structural repair and reuse have been successfully conducted and are discussed in this section.

5.1. Repair of damaged elements

Repairing existing structures instead of demolition and reconstruction can have very substantial environmental benefits. The prospect of WAAM for on-site printing lends itself to retrofitting or repair of damaged structural elements, with more flexibility than existing methods such as the addition of plates or fibre-reinforced polymers (FRPs). Ghafoori et al. [77] adopted WAAM for the fatigue repair of precracked steel plates, as shown in Fig. 31. The addition of WAAM material was shown to reduce the stress level at the crack section via an enhanced cross-sectional area, and also to generate beneficial compressive residual stress at the crack tip during cooling. The fatigue tests showed that the propagation of existing cracks was inhibited after repair by the WAAM material, and more effectively than using FRP strengthening. It was found that the as-built profile of the WAAM deposits did however lead to increased stress concentrations, as also observed in previous fatigue tests [78,79], but this could be mitigated by post machining (Fig. 31). The influence of printing strategies on the efficiency of strengthening was further investigated by means of finite element modelling in [80]. Mavros et al. [81] employed WAAM for the repair of historic masonry structures, where custom-fit steel reinforcing meshes, tailored to the profile of mortar joints by means of 3D laser scanning, were printed by WAAM and embedded within the masonry wall specimens, as shown in Fig. 32. Compared with plain masonry walls, the WAAM-repaired specimens exhibited notable improvements in terms of both the load-carrying capacity (3.1 times under diagonal compression) and ductility, with minimal disturbance to the original appearance. Kang et al. [82–84] employed laser cladding, a laser and powder-based DED technique, to repair corroded structural steel CHS stub columns by depositing material onto the corroded region, as shown in Fig. 33. The compression test results confirmed that both the stiffness and load-carrying capacity of the damaged CHS stub columns could be fully restored or even enhanced after repair. Similarly, thermal spraying, especially cold spraying that has undergone substantial development in recent decades, has been used to restore corroded or damaged components in various engineering fields [85,86]. Despite using different methods of metal deposition, the concept of structural repair by targeted additions of material via metal AM is also applicable to WAAM. Additionally, Du et al. [87] presented the concept of wire arc additive remanufacturing (WAAR), i.e. using WAAM to repair or remanufacture damaged components, together with a collection of example applications of WAAR in e.g. the aerospace, marine and automotive industries;

Fig. 31. WAAM-repaired steel plates with as-built (left) and machined (right) geometry [77].

the scope can be extended to structural repair in the construction industry.

5.2. Facilitating reuse

After structures reach their end-of-life, most steel elements are currently recycled through remelting, which is a rather energy intensive process. In contrast, direct reuse [88] of structural steel without remelting minimises the reoccurring embodied carbon and could bring considerable environmental savings [89]. However, challenges associated with the degradation of structural performance (from e.g. corrosion, plastic deformation or fatigue), the occurrence of damage (e.g. during deconstruction) and the presence of holes (e.g. for bolted connections), as well as the logistical issues associated with the availability of elements of the required dimensions, often hinder the direct reuse of the reclaimed steel. WAAM brings about new opportunities to overcome these challenges. WAAM can be used to adapt the geometry of the reclaimed steel elements (such as increasing the member length or filling bolt holes) according to the demand in new applications. Furthermore, the strategies described above for strengthening or repairing structural elements using WAAM can be employed to restore (or even enhance as necessary) the structural performance of the reclaimed structural steelwork. A growing body of research has been devoted to repurposing end-of-life metal parts through hybrid manufacturing (i.e. combining metal AM and subtractive manufacturing) [90], predominantly in the context of aerospace, automotive and mechanical engineering, while research is needed to unleash the potential of WAAM to facilitate steel reuse in the construction sector.

6. Challenges and opportunities

Alongside the encouraging outcomes from the early research endeavours associated with hybrid construction, challenges and

Fig. 32. Printing of WAAM steel reinforcing mesh (left) and reinforced masonry wall specimen (right) [81].

Fig. 33. Damaged CHS steel member repaired by laser cladding [82].

opportunities regarding sustainability, economic viability, printability, on-site construction applications, multi-material construction and structural design have also been identified, as discussed in this section.

6.1. Sustainability

The geometric flexibility of WAAM brings significant potential for reducing the embodied carbon in structures; hybrid construction featuring the combination of WAAM with conventional steelwork offers a practical means of maximising this potential. A life-cycle assessment was performed by Shah et al. [91] to compare the environmental impacts of conventionally produced I-section beams and WAAM optimised steel beams. It was found that WAAM brings a positive impact on carbon emissions if 50 % or less material is used, which is achievable by exploiting the geometric freedom of WAAM through structural optimisation. At present, linear, stiffness-based optimisation has been the most widely used approach and has been shown to provide reasonable results in many cases; yet optimisation approaches that incorporate material and geometric nonlinearities and feature objectives other than stiffness (e.g. strength and ductility) at a reasonable computational cost are still desired, in order to provide more rigorous solutions and to maximise the benefits offered by WAAM. It was also highlighted that increasing the deposition rate of WAAM, which has been a trending topic in research and industry [92], can significantly reduce the carbon footprint. Baqershahi et al. [93] explored the environmental performance of hybrid construction by considering a series of idealised 2D beams. Similar to the findings for hybrid columns by Gardner et al. [47], a small amount of WAAM material, when strategically located and optimised in hybrid beams, could bring about disproportionate savings in the overall material consumption. As the proportion of WAAM material increased, further material savings were achievable, but to a lesser extent, and the higher energy consumption per unit weight for WAAM would eventually outweigh the environmental benefits from the reduced material usage. Therefore, carbon emissions were minimised for hybrid beams with an appropriate balance between conventionally produced and optimised WAAM materials, confirming the strong potential environmental credentials of hybrid construction and, again, the pivotal role of optimisation. It was also pointed out that the scope for material savings, and thus the extent of environmental benefits, vary depending on the structural scenarios. Hence, further cradle-to-gate life cycle assessments of different hybrid construction designs are needed to quantify the carbon footprint and inform the optimal hybridisation strategy for the implementation of WAAM.

6.2. Economic viability

Key to opening the market for WAAM in construction is its economic competitiveness. To date, most cost modelling studies [94–97] on WAAM have been conducted in the context of mechanical, automotive and aerospace engineering, where the main economic benefit is the reduced buy-to-fly (BTF) or equivalent ratio (typically below 2) for WAAM compared with that for subtractive manufacturing (up to 20) [98], coupled with the relatively high raw material costs of e.g. titanium alloys. A notable case study was conducted by Kokare et al. [95], where the economic performance of WAAM and CNC milling for the manufacture of a steel wall was compared via life-cycle cost modelling. The results showed that a BTF ratio of 9 for CNC milling is needed to break even (although this will vary for different material types and part geometries), and this is expected to reduce with less manual supervision for WAAM and material savings from AM-oriented optimisation.

In the construction sector, formative manufacturing and manual welding are the primary methods of steel fabrication. The main potential economic benefits offered by WAAM are the material savings from the increased material efficiency achieved through optimisation, as well as the reduced labour cost from the higher level of automation. Furthermore, structural applications are accepting of the as-built geometry of WAAM, which eliminates the post-processing cost. The labour cost of WAAM is expected to drop with time, as the need for manual supervision is constantly reducing and the labour will be spread across a higher number of robots for production at scale [3]. The increase in deposition rates as WAAM technology advances should also reduce production times and the associated machine, shield gas and labour costs.

Hybrid construction minimises the influence of the production time and cost of WAAM by using a relatively small amount of WAAM material, yet still allows the benefits in terms of geometric flexibility and automation to be exploited to a great extent. Combined with the positive environmental and social impacts (e.g. the improvement of working conditions and the generation of employment [95]), it is expected that the financial barrier to the use of WAAM at scale in construction will be overcome.

6.3. Printability

In hybrid construction, conventional structural steel elements are often used as the substrate for WAAM. Distortion or alteration of the mechanical properties of the substrate (i.e. the steel structure) is likely to be more crucial than usual because of its subsequent load-bearing requirements in hybrid construction. Complications for printing could also arise from e.g. the irregular substrate geometry and interference with the existing steel parts. An example of this is the addition of optimised WAAM stiffeners for hot-rolled steel I-sections, as presented in [50], where the torch angle had to be adjusted during deposition to avoid collision with the I-section flanges. Facing the greater printability challenges, more sophisticated control over the WAAM process is required for the realisation of hybrid construction designs. Advanced process controls, e.g. non-planar layers and adaptive process parameters and welding positions, have been developed for WAAM with the assistance of laser scanning and artificial intelligence in the laboratory environment [99–102]. The wider implementation of these techniques will alleviate the design and manufacturing constraints for hybrid construction.

6.4. Multi-material construction

Multi-material construction, i.e. combining multiple materials in a single structural element, enables the relevant properties to be customised in response to the structural, environmental and aesthetic demands, bringing opportunities to optimise material utilisation and ultimately facilitate more sustainable construction [103]. Multi-material WAAM can be achieved through the use of multiple wire

feeds or novel wires (stranded or cored) [104], enabling the manufacture of bi-metallic [105] and functionally graded [106] materials, the characteristics of which can be tailored to suit different application demands. In the context of structural engineering, Weber et al. [107] successfully employed WAAM to produce a series of steel beams with tailored bending moment capacities by varying steel grades and wall thicknesses along the member length.

There is also broad scope for the hybridisation of WAAM and other constructional materials. WAAM has been adopted to produce steel reinforcement for concrete to achieve greater automation and accommodate geometrically complex structural design, with possibilities to customise bar profiles [108,109] and optimise reinforcement layouts [110]. Studies into composite structural elements featuring WAAM have also been performed; for example, in [111,112], a series of experiments on concrete-filled WAAM steel tubes were presented, where the WAAM outer tubes were shown to provide excellent circumferential confinement and enhanced interfacial bond behaviour due to the surface undulations. It is envisaged that multi-material hybrid construction featuring WAAM will play an important role in the future construction industry with higher design flexibility, material efficiency and sustainability.

6.5. On-site construction applications

The transformation of construction towards greater automation is deemed to be inevitable; hence, on-site WAAM is envisaged to be an important element of construction in the future. At present, on-site printing in general faces challenges related to the positional accuracy, variable environmental and site conditions, logistics and so on, yet encouraging research progress has been made on addressing these issues. The feasibility of on-site concrete 3D printing has been demonstrated in research [113,114] and a number of practical pilot projects [115,116]. On-site robotic welding has also been increasingly used in construction [117,118]. Lange et al. [41] adopted WAAM to manufacture a steel bridge in-situ over a stream in Darmstadt, as shown in Fig. 1 (b), although the welding robot remained stationary and operated in an enclosure.

The use of WAAM on-site will expand the scope of hybrid construction to the retrofitting and repair of existing structures in response to hazards or changes in demands. This will enable the service lives of existing structures to be extended and reduce the need for demolition and reconstruction, which has significant implications for decarbonisation. Also, the WAAM strengthening approaches presented in previous sections, despite having been discussed mainly in pre-construction settings, could also be applied in on-site scenarios.

6.6. Structural design

Verification of the structural safety and reliability of hybrid steel structures is essential before the widespread implementation in practice. Consideration must be given to both serviceability and ultimate limit state performance, as well as to long term effects, such as corrosion [35] and fatigue [119], and extreme loading scenarios, including fire [120] and seismic actions [121]. Thus far, the structural verification of WAAM parts has been achieved mainly by means of exhaustive physical experiments, such as for the MX3D bridge [39]. However, this is deemed to be impractical for the general use of WAAM, and safe and efficient structural design methods are needed. For structural elements of with lower geometric complexity, the existing codified design methods for conventional steel structures could remain applicable after appropriate modifications. For instance, for the WAAM-strengthened I-section columns presented in Section 2.1, the existing Eurocode 3 column buckling curve [122] was shown to yield reasonably accurate and safe-sided resistance predictions when the added WAAM material was duly accounted for in the calculation of the relative slenderness $\bar{\lambda} =$

Fig. 34. Comparisons of bare and WAAM-strengthened column buckling test results with EC3 buckling curve [47].

$\sqrt{N_{c,R}/N_{cr}}$ (where $N_{c,R}$ is the cross-sectional resistance to axial compression and N_{cr} is the Euler buckling load) [47], as shown in Fig. 34, where N_u is the ultimate load and A_{min} is the minimum cross-sectional area along the member length. For structural elements of higher geometric complexity (e.g. topology optimised joints), a finite element modelling-based design approach [40,123] is likely to be appropriate, and should be streamlined with suitable simplifications made for practicality. Preliminary investigations into the structural simulation of WAAM elements have been carried out [124,125]. Finally, statistical analysis based on a larger body of experimental data is required to derive suitable design values of geometric and mechanical properties for WAAM material [126], as well as suitable partial safety factors for the structural design of hybrid components.

7. Conclusions

A new form of hybrid construction, in which conventional structural elements are coupled with wire arc additive manufacturing (WAAM) to combine the merits from both and mitigate the limitations of WAAM in terms of productivity and costs, has recently emerged. In this paper, a review of research advances on hybrid construction, including a series of ongoing studies at Imperial College London, has been presented. WAAM has been used to enhance the structural performance of conventional structural steel members subjected to compression, bending and tension, by both adding material and making positive use of thermally-induced residual stresses and deformations. Physical experiments showed a disproportionate increase in the load-carrying capacity after strengthening, as well as a reduction in net deflections for the case of beams. WAAM can also be used to create optimised stiffeners to locally strengthen structural sections, offering reduced material use and eliminating the need for manual welding. The feasibility has been demonstrated for I-sections subjected to concentrated transverse loading, while the application to generic plated elements is under exploration. Joints generally represent only a small portion of a structure, but tend to have intricate geometry, and hence there is considerable scope for the utilisation of WAAM and structural optimisation. A number of studies have been conducted to explore the optimisation and additive manufacturing of joints between conventionally produced beams and columns, and in tubular trusses, spatial grid structures and so on. A new form of hybrid joint, where WAAM material is used partially or in addition to existing joints has been proposed in recent studies to facilitate connections with conventional members or to strengthen the joint region. Research has also been dedicated to different means of connecting conventionally produced and WAAM parts. Furthermore, the flexibility and thermal effects of WAAM can be utilised for structural retrofitting and repair. An experimental proof of concept has been conducted, where WAAM was

adopted to strengthen damaged steel plates against fatigue. Last but not least, there are opportunities to employ WAAM to adapt reclaimed structural steel components and facilitate their reuse. In general, structural optimisation plays a vital role in harnessing the geometric flexibility of WAAM in hybrid structures. The influence of the WAAM process on the conventional structural steelwork, e.g. residual stresses and deformations arising from the thermal cycles, should be considered, and, when possible, leveraged to create a positive impact on the overall structural performance.

Amid the emerging research into the hybrid use of WAAM, the key challenges and opportunities associated with hybrid construction have also been discussed. The potential of hybrid construction and structural optimisation to reduce the embodied carbon in structures has been clearly demonstrated, and future research is needed to guide the implementation of WAAM in hybrid structures and maximise the environmental benefits. The influence of the relatively high production time and cost of WAAM, a major barrier to its wider adoption, can be minimised through hybrid construction. Printability issues may arise when WAAM material is deposited onto conventional structural elements; in this case, adaptive control of the printing process would be required. Multi-material construction, featuring multi-material WAAM or a hybridisation of WAAM and other constructional materials, brings new opportunities to customise material properties according to the demands of the application and further improve the material efficiency. As on-site printing technology matures, it is envisaged that it will soon be possible to use WAAM for the retrofitting and repair of existing structures, which could have a profound impact on the decarbonisation of construction. Finally, safe, efficient and user-friendly structural design methods are needed to put hybrid construction into the hands of structural practitioners. Overall, hybrid construction presents a viable pathway towards the widespread adoption of WAAM in the construction sector, and is expected to be a key driver for a more sustainable and automated construction in the foreseeable future.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Xin Meng: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Leroy Gardner:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

We wish to draw the attention of the Editor to the following facts which may be considered as potential conflicts of interest and to significant financial contributions to this work. We wish to confirm that there are no known conflicts of interest associated with this publication and there has been no significant financial support for this work that could have influenced its outcome.

We confirm that the manuscript has been read and approved by all named authors and that there are no other persons who satisfied the criteria for authorship but are not listed. We further confirm that the order of authors listed in the manuscript has been approved by all of us.

We confirm that we have given due consideration to the protection of intellectual property associated with this work and that there are no impediments to publication, including the timing of publication, with respect to intellectual property. In so doing we confirm that we have followed the regulations of our institutions concerning intellectual property.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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